

Role of RTE, Free Education, Compulsory Education and Mid Day Meal on Status of Literacy in India

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ABSTRACT

India's literacy rate has made significant progress in scientific independence. The country's literacy rate increased from 18.32% in 1951 to 74.04% in 2011. For decades, the literacy rate has increased by 57.49. The absolute number of non-literate people decreased from 328.88 million in 1991 to 302 million in 2001. They expect that by 2007, the literacy rate will reach 75%. The proportion of women also rose from 52.22% in 1991 to 74.04% in 2011, at 21.83 percentage points, and the proportion of men rose from 64.13% to 82.14%. 18.1 percentage points over the same period.

Keywords: RTE, Free Education, Compulsory Education And Mid Day Meal On Status Of Literacy In India

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the deterioration of the situation has forced Mahatma Gandhi to provoke a call for universal education in 1937. He called for adequate funding for universal education, but their response was to use alcohol sales if they had. This means that he either gives up the banned stance or abandons the state-supported universal education. He clearly stated: "The cruelest irony of the new reform is that we only have the income of liquor. In order to educate our children . He By asking for self-funded education, he solved what he called "educational problems", which was later called nai talim.

Gopal Krishna Gokhale on March 18, 1910,
"request that the following resolution be submitted to the Council for consideration. ... The State should accept the same responsibility of the mass education

that most civilized governments have already fulfilled in this country, and should develop a well-considered plan and stick to it until now. ...the welfare of millions of children waiting to be affected by education depends on it..."

in the Imperial Legislative Council to seek "free and compulsory primary education" in India. However, this initiative must be seen as part of a series of events:

1870: Britain passed the "Compulsory Education Law"

1882: Indian Board of Education: Indian leaders demand a public education and compulsory education bill.

1893: The Maharaja of Vadodara introduces compulsory education to boys at Amreli Taluk.

1906: The Maharaja of Vadodara extends compulsory education to other parts of the state.

1906: Gopal Krishna Gokhale asks the Imperial Legislative Council to introduce free compulsory education

1910: Gokhale proposes private member Bill (rejected)

1917: Vithalbhai Patel successfully passed the bill - passed the first compulsory education law (commonly known as Patel)

1918: Every province of British India receives compulsory education in its regulations

1930: The Hartog Committee's recommendations for improving quality (reducing attention to quantity) hamper the spread and development of primary education.

However, many of these initiatives have not been implemented seriously; lack of resources and enforcement are the main reasons.

OBJECT OF STUDY:-

1. Effect of RTE on Status of Literacy In India.
2. Effect of Free Education on Status of Literacy In India.
3. Effect of Compulsory Education And Mid Day Meal On Status Of Literacy In India.

THE CHALLENGES FOR RTE

The main challenge is to implement a 25% reservation for poor students, to allow all children to go to the fifth grade, to achieve acceptable standard learning levels, to supervise the recognition of private schools, and to establish a well-functioning school management committee, all of which are adopted. A similar mechanism is completed in all states and territories.

MEANING OF “FREE EDUCATION”

Free education usually means exemption from tuition fees. But tuition is only part of the cost of education, and poor families often fail to raise the other costs of education. These may include textbooks, photocopies and writing materials, uniforms, transportation, education and support materials for children with disabilities (hearing aids, glasses, braille books, crutches, etc.), and even library fees, laboratory fees, and more. According to tuition fees.

The phenomenon of dropping out of school is especially related to the fact that parents cannot be able to spend some time in the basic education process, whether it is a daughter or a daughter's education. With this in mind, the Act in Section 3(2) enforces the requirement that “any child may not pay for any fees or expenses that may prevent him or her from completing basic education.

“Free” The list of free rights is expressly provided in Article 5(1) of the Model Rules, but is not restrictive; in accordance with Article 3(2) of the Act, if in addition to Article 5(1) of the Model Rules Any other fees or expenses, such as free accommodation for children whose parents immigrate, prevent children from pursuing or completing basic course education, which the state must provide.

In countries like India where the vast majority of parents are poor, moving for work, without support

systems, forcing them to be punished means imposing their poverty - this is not their choice. As the well-known educator J.P. Naik once wittily commented, if parents are sent to prison for not sending their children to school, the parents in the prison may be more than the children in the school!

IF PARENTS DON'T SEND THEIR CHILDREN TO SCHOOL

Section (10) of the Act stipulates that parents are responsible for ensuring that their children attend school without any penalty. This means that SMC members, local authorities and the entire community must persuade reluctant parents to perform their duties. For child labourers and street children, the government must ensure that they are not forced to work and provide them with schools, and in many cases may be accommodation. Parents and communities that traditionally prohibit adolescent girls from attending school or indulging child marriage must be persuaded, otherwise child marriage must be invoked. Civil society intervention is crucial here.

MID DAY MEAL SCHEME

The programme will be phased in, starting with 1995-1996, with all governments, local institutions and primary schools where the federal territory (UT) is located.

This is the year 1995-1996, which will begin in all 2368 Reconstruction Public Distribution System (RPDS)/Employment Assurance Program (EAS) blocks and 40 Low Female Literacy (LFL) blocks. A state like Punjab does not have an EAS/RPDS blocking program that will start with the lfl block, a block with a female literacy rate below the national average. In states and UTs such as Goa, Dehli, Pondicherry and Chandigarh without RPDS or LFL blocks, primary schools that inform slums will be covered. In the 1996-1997 school year, the program will be extended to all remaining Lfl blocks in 2005, with female literacy rates below the national average. From 1997 to 1998, the program will be extended to all other primary schools.

The central government will assist local institutions such as Panchayat and Nagarpalikas to implement the program, providing thatched food wheat to the nearest Indian food company (FCI), 100 grams per student per day. The main principles for the distribution of food revenue are as follows:

The district will be the assigned unit. Talika will be the unit of distribution. According to the 1993-1994 enrollment data collected by the Sixth All India Education Survey, each quarter will be based on the Indian government through FCI to distribute food revenue.

This is the second quarter of the program's start in a region, which will be based on closed data received from FCI and regional smart use certificates and registration data received from the state.

The distribution of food distributed from the FCI will be valid for the quarter in which it is allocated and cannot be carried over to the next quarter.

Based on the distribution of the Indian government for each region, regional collectors will further assign the rights of each school and local authority and will indicate who will cancel the food gains.

CONCLUSION

According to the MDM guidelines, the Department of School Education and Literacy (DoSeL) of MHRD distributes food to states each year. These grants are based on the number of students enrolled in the school and the working days approved by the PAB in

previous years. Primary schools (standards 1-5) and higher primary schools (standards 6-8) are allocated separately. The monthly grant for the sixth month is a temporary transfer made during the first week of February of the previous fiscal year. The amount of food distributed depends on the number of children approved by the PAB and the number of school days worked. The second and final allocation was made during the first week of August and was based on a Certificate of Use (UC) issued by the state government detailing the food received and actually consumed at the school/cooking facility level 4 in the previous financial year. Quantity. These UCs will be submitted by the states by June 30th. The second allocation is made after taking into account the unused balance available to the state/UT (based on the previous year's allocated balance and current allocation)

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